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Principals Management and Organization Skills for The Administration of Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined Principals Management and Organization Skills for The Administration of Secondary Schools In Rivers State. Two research questions and two corresponding hypotheses were used for the study. The research design adopted was descriptive survey design. The population of this study consisted of all the 276 secondary schools in Rivers State. Out of the 276 principals, a sample of 202 principals representing 73% served as the study participants. The respondents were selected through the use of stratified random sampling technique. This means that each of the local government area served as a stratum. A self-constructed instrument titled “Principals Management and Organization Skills for The Administration Questionnaire (PMOSAQ). The Cronbach Alpha method was used to establish the internal consistency of the instrument. The instrument was administered to 20 teachers who were not part of the sample for the study. The reliability for time management skill was 0.62 and for principals’ organizing skill was 0.56 respectively. The various coefficients were high enough and guaranteed the use of the instrument for the study. The research questions were answered using mean, standard deviation statistics and rank order scores of respondents. From the findings, the study concluded that when principals’ managerial skills are being used effectively by the principal, there will also be effective administration of secondary schools in Rivers State. Based on the findings of the study, the study recommended thus among others that School administrators should utilize the non-verbal and prioritizing skills meant for proper running of the school.

Keywords: Organization Skills, Principal, Secondary Schools, Management

INTRODUCTION

Education as a universal practice engaged in all societies at all levels of development has brought restoration to individuals and the societies at large. Education is an instrument for human development for productive life and peaceful co-existence. It is also seen as a process whereby one generation passes on to the next its knowledge and wisdom. In this context of education, a citizen is transformed as the needs of the society change. It is for these reasons that emphasis are placed on the three major roles of education in society, namely; meeting the needs of the people, developing needed manpower for societal development. Secondary education in Nigeria is geared towards providing necessary skills for useful living with the society and to prepare students to continue with higher education. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN) (2013), in her national Policy on Education, secondary education is the education given to children after primary education and before tertiary education.

It is aimed at preparing an individual for useful living within the society and higher education. At this stage of education, many activities take place. These activities involve different persons’ ideologies and objectives coordinated also by different persons from different backgrounds, to make the school system functional. From the above scenario, school administration is critical to the entire education process. Administration is a process by which set objectives are determined and actualized through the group and mutual human endeavors in a comfortable atmosphere. Administration takes place in a formal organization. School being a formal

organization, engages in administrative processes to achieve the expected outcome. School administration is a social process concerned with identifying, maintaining, stimulating, controlling and unifying formally and informally organized human and material energies with a targeted system designed to achieve predetermined objective. School administration concerns students, teachers, material resources, rules, regulations, policies and harmonization of relationships and additionally, it concerns the utilization of available resources and harmonization or relationships and interactions in a suitable environment in order to ensure the attainment of the goals of teaching and learning.

In every effective secondary school there is effective administration. In the administration of schools, the principal is central. The principal is the administrative head of a secondary school. The principal is the chief executive officer in the Nigeria secondary school system. The principal is regarded as the most important functionary in the secondary school system. The principal performs a good number of administrative functions in the effort to achieve the goals and objectives for which secondary schools are set up. He/she is responsible for all the personnel in a particular school, including training, evaluation and motivation as well as students' management and development. The principal must aim at arousing the interest of the students and teachers by creating a good atmosphere for teaching and learning in the school environment through management skills.

Managerial skills have to do with peculiar sets of activities performed by a person or people which lead to positive results. The management skills are said to be behavioral, they are not human possessed attributes. These activities are under the control of the individual. Furthermore, principalship capabilities are not usually innate. In fact an effective principal is made not born because their expertise and knowledge have to be constantly refined over time. There is the need to possess adequate and sound managerial skills by administrators to ensure administrative effectiveness. Administering the affair of a school is a herculean task and to a very large extent, the success of school organization is dependent upon many factors. One of such factors is management skills of which the administrator will not be effective without putting them into practice and affect them. The success of a manager depends on his ability to discharge his managerial functions and make judicious use of his managerial skills. The skills are designed to help them improve their managerial competencies as administrators. In the quest to make a better administration, Muraina (2006) outlined some specific managerial skills that principal should put into practices for goal achievement, they are: communication skills, decision making skills, disciplinary skills and organizing skills.

Organization skill of the principals emanate from element of management. Organization is the process of arranging and allocating work, authority and resources among organization membership for the pursuit of the goals of the organization.

Statement of the problem

Secondary education is the bridge between the primary and tertiary levels, and also very important in the development of middle level manpower. It therefore deserves a lot of attention. One of the important factors that guarantee the delivery of quality secondary education is effective administration. The principal ensures that the day to day activities of the school and both the human and material resources are well coordinated to ensure that the goals of the school are achieved towards effectiveness and efficiency in the administration of the schools. Observation has shown that most secondary school principals lack the necessary administrative skills such as time management, decision making skill, organizing skill, to mention just a few, for proper management of secondary schools in River State, and this have a negative impact on delivery of effective secondary education. These skills are instrumental for better management of secondary schools by the principals. Could it be that the principals lack the basic administrative skills? It is in this light of concern that the researcher was bothered to investigate principals management and organization skills for the administration of secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate the principals' managerial skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State.

Specifically, the objectives of this study sought to:

- Find out the principals' time management skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State.

- Determine the principals' organizing skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in the study:

- What are the principals' time management skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State?
- What are the principals' organizing skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study

- Ho1: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the time management skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State.
- Ho2: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the organizing skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State.

Concept of Management

Every institution, organization, sect, household and business needs proper management to ensure a smooth running of such organizational set up. An institution such as an educational institution, if not properly managed, planned and controlled cannot achieve success. In a nutshell, good management needs to be established. Human, material and financial resources must be present to achieve managerial goals and objectives. If proper manpower budget is not well planned, the Organization would be faced with a high risk failure. Individual staffs control all the other resources of the Organization. Cole (2002) posited that human resources planning is not just a number game, even though labour statistics are an important element in it. Human resource planning is as much, if not more, concerned with the quality of personnel and with their deployment throughout the Organization. Maxwell (2001) posited that stop trying to grow your Organization. Work on people's attitudes. If you do that, your organization will experience 10% growth overnight. In Organizations the most difficult resources to manage are human beings. This is why there is need to properly select personnel sensitive positions within an Organization.

Thus, Management in a general context involves the act of getting things done and evaluating performance which is known as controlling. Controlling is one of the components of management that ensure effectiveness job delivery in work place. It is on this note that James (2000) posited that management is a process of planning, organizing, leading and controlling the work of organizing members and of using all available resources to reach Organizational goals. Managers are group of persons responsible for directing the efforts aimed at helping and achieving Organizational goal. James (2000) further explained management as a way of handling activities. These activities include planning, Organizing, Controlling and leading.

Principal's Managerial skills

In every organization, it is the duty of the head to take up vital administrative roles for the smooth running of that organization. The same situation is practically applied to the school principals as heads of educational institutions at the secondary level. Meanwhile, management first of all can be seen as an administrative task that deals with utilization of organizational resources for the achievement of organizational goals and objectives. According to Wehrich, Cannice and Koonez, (2010), management is the process of designing and maintaining an environment in which individuals working together in group, efficiently accomplish selected aims' we therefore talk of management when the activities of different individuals and groups are harmonized for the achievement of organizational goals. It is the process of coordinating what the various units of an organization spent their time in doing in other to achieve a single objective.

Every organization management has a certain principles that includes, the subordination of people interest; unity of command; work division, initiative and spirit de corps; materials and social order authority; unity of direction; stability; disciplines; remuneration; scalar chain; equity; centralization. It is expected that any management strategy adopted by an organization, educational economic, educational or financial should achieve some of the above mentioned principles. In that these principles have limited time which must be fulfilled. Management is very important in the educational sector for the application of human and material resources for the benefit of groups or individuals. On the other hand, Nwaoji, (2005) described skills as the

ability of person to perform a given task well as a result a training and practice. Management skills have to do with peculiar sets of activities performed by a person or people which lead to positive results. The management skills are said to be behavioral, they are not human possessed attributes. These activities are under the control of the individual. In the quest to make a better administration, Muraina (2006), outlined some specific managerial skills that principals should put into practice for goals achievement. They are communication skills, decision making skills, time management skills and organizing skills respectively.

Organizing Skills adopted for Secondary School Administration

Organizing skill is the element of administration that is concerned with relating all the components of an organization into a co-ordinate whole so as to achieve a set goal, Obi (2003). Organizing entails identifying the task to be done, arranging them into jobs or roles for individuals and allocating them among employees in units or Departments. Okwori (2011) stated that organizing function involves division of task or work, departmentalizing and delegation of authority and responsibility. Organizing therefore is the element of administration that is concerned with relating all the components of an organization into a co-ordinate whole so as to achieve a set goal. Organizing entails identifying the done, arranging them into jobs or roles for individuals and allocating them among employees in units or Departments. In the same vein, Katz (1955) recognized some other management skills principals must possess for effective secondary school administration as conceptual skill, technical skill and human skill.

Conceptual Skill: Conceptual skill has to do with the mental ability of an administrator to identify and evaluate difficult situations (Miles, 2002). It is on this note that Sen and Saxena (2009) stated that conceptual skills are broader and more self-actualized. They include the ability to see organization in the context of its industry, the ability to visualize a future course of action based on current organizational and industry trends, the ability to analyze and diagnose complex situations and the ability to understand the interrelationships at work in the organization Sen and Saxena (2009).

It is important for school administrators to build up their conceptual skill in conjunction with their human and technical skills. Building the human and technical skills should not be the only areas of concentration or areas to be focus on; rather emphasis should be placed on the conceptual skill of every administrator. An administrator must have a mental ability to diagnose and analyze cases that seem difficult in the school environment. These tasks require conceptual skill. Decision making for example requires school administrators to spot problems, identify alternatives that can correct them, evaluate those alternatives, and select the best one. Administrators can be technically and interpersonally competent, yet some fail because of their inability to rationally process and interpret information (Miles, 2002).

Management skills programme should be imitated on these three levels in order to equip secondary school administrators to fulfill their roles successfully. According to McDermott 2011 management skills development is an effective strategy for keeping administrator abreast with the latest development in their respective fields of study. It is imperative that school administrators keep up with the latest development in their respective fields and at same time manage an ever-changing workforce operating in the dynamic environment. It is on this not that Ndu (2009) discussed internship and monitoring as veritable tool for skills development. Apart from internship and monitoring, other programmes that can be used to develop conceptual skill are role-playing and membership of 'think-tank' committees or groups.

Technical skill: this entails proficiency of a school administrator to apply specialized expertise in the discharge of his functional or official duties (Adler and Bartholomew 2002). Technical skills include skilled performance of specific tasks, expertise in a specific field or industry, specialized training and the ability to apply specialized knowledge to task and objectives Korman (2010). Technical training can be acquired through coaching, training, educational programme and job rotation. Dunnette (2006) opined that via extensive formal education, administrator learn the special knowledge and practices of their field of course, administrators do not have monopoly on technical skills and not all technical skills have to be learned in school or formal training programmes. However, all jobs require some specialized expertise, and every administrator needs to develop their technical skills on the job.

Human skill: this skill refers to an administrator's ability to function or work with, understand and motivate individuals or group of persons (Sheromon, 2002). Human skills include the ability to work effectively with others, motivate workers, resolve conflicts delegate roles and communicate objectives clearly (Nwagboa,

2004). Applying human skill in solving organizational problems is not stereotyped as individuals and situations differ in various dimensions. More so, it is important for administrators to build up their human skills alongside technical skills because without building up the human skills an administrator may fail in his or her administrative responsibility. Some administrators are technically proficient but interpersonally incompetent. They might be poor listeners, unable to understand the needs of others, or have difficulty managing conflicts. Since administrators get things done through and with other people, they must have good human skills to communicate, motivate and delegate (Olusegun, 2008). In order to build this skill is through emotional intelligence (EI); which involves the ability to monitor one's own and other feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them, and to use this information to guide one's thinking and action. It is on this note the effective use of emotion is important to the function of a successful leadership. They further explained that leaders are emotional guides influencing not only follower emotions but also follower action through relationship management, motivational appeal, and goal-setting and the leader's emotional intelligence is necessary to effectively perform these efforts.

Theory

The theory on which this study was based was the efficiency and effectiveness of organization theory propounded by Chester Bernard (1938). The theory states that the function of the Chief executive of an organization is to ensure efficiency and effectiveness in the organizational, efficiency being employee centered and effectiveness being employer and task oriented. According to the theory, effectiveness in the organization deals with the accomplishment of the organizational objectives through task oriented. According to the theory, effectiveness in the organization deals with the accomplishment of the organizational objectives through task related activities which help the organization to attain its stated goals. On the other hand, efficiency entails all efforts geared towards attaining staff welfare and better working condition. In this case, the manner in which the chief executive handles these as to establish synergy between the duo is of importance to the life and existence of the organization.

The theory of efficiency and effectiveness further advocated that a synergy must exist between the availability of the quantity and quality of input and prudent management of all the resources, both human and material of the organization, if the organizational goals will be achieved and the organization continues to exist. The theory is very relevant to this study because it clearly explains how management skills lead to effectiveness in secondary school administration. As an administrator, he is to manage his staff and students using the needed skills to ensure effective administration of the school to achieve the necessary goals. The principal is the administrative head of a school and by so, shouldered the responsibility of the day to day running of the school. This implies that he/she directs and coordinates all activities to ensure efficiency and effectiveness in the school system, the principal should possess all the administrative skills, such as time management skill, decision-making skill, organizing skill etc, which will make him or her function effectively. In other words, when a principal possesses all the necessary administrative skills, he/she becomes capable to function as both manager who is in charge of the school and also, resource person, through whom ideas for proper operation of the school system emanate from.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted was descriptive survey design. The population of this study consisted of all the 276 secondary schools in Rivers State. Out of the 276 principals, a sample of 202 principals representing 73% served as the study participants. The respondents were selected through the use of stratified random sampling technique. This means that each of the local government area served as a stratum. A self-constructed instrument titled "Principals Management And Organization Skills For The Administration Questionnaire (PMOSAQ). The cronbach Alpha method was used to establish the internal consistency of the instrument. The instrument was administered to 20 teachers who were not part of the sample for the study. The reliability for time management skill was 0.62 and for principals' organizing skill was 0.56 respectively. The various coefficients were high enough and guaranteed the use of the instrument for the study. The research questions were answered using mean, standard deviation statistics and rank order scores of respondents. The criterion mean of 2.50 will be used to take decisions, any mean rating below 2.50 will be regarded as disagreed while

those above 2.50 will be seen as agreed. The criterion mean will be obtained thus, (SA) = 4 + (A) = 3 + (D) = 2 + (SD) = 1 = = 2.50. The hypotheses were tested using z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. Which is a z-critical of 1.96. any response therefore, with a calculated z value above 1.96 was rejected and below 1.96 was accepted.

RESULTS

Presentation and Analysis of Data to Research Questions

Research Question two

What are the principals' time management skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean scores of male and female principals on the time management skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State.

S/N	Items	MALE		FEMALE		xx	RANK	REMARK
		N	x	N	X			
1.	Delegation skill	95	3.45	105	3.00	3.23	1 st	Agree
2.	Organizing skill	95	2.97	105	3.10	3.04	2 nd	Agree
3.	Prioritizing skill	95	2.66	105	2.14	2.40	5 th	Disagree
4.	Planning skill	95	3.03	105	2.44	2.74	4 th	Agree
5.	Communication skill	95	3.05	105	2.45	2.75	3 rd	Agree

Aggregate mean = 3.07 and 2.66

The result as revealed in Table 1 indicated that respondents agreed to delegation skill with mean scores of 3.45 and 3.00, organizing skill with mean scores of 2.97 and 3.10, communication skill with mean scores of 3.05 and 2.45, planning skill with mean scores of 3.03 and 2.44, and they disagreed to prioritizing skill with mean scores of 2.66 and 2.14 as the time management skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State. However, the aggregate mean shows that male principals agreed to the time management skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State than the female principals.

Research Question Two

What are the principals' organizing skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean scores of male and female principals on the organizing skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State.

S/N	Items	MALE		FEMALE		xx	RANK	REMARK
		N	x	N	X			
6.	Conceptual Skill	95	2.40	105	2.34	2.37	5 th	Disagree
7	Technical Skill	95	2.35	105	2.49	2.42	4 th	Disagree
8.	Coordinating Skill	95	3.30	105	3.60	3.45	1 st	Agree
9.	Time management skill	95	3.73	105	2.44	3.09	2 nd	Agree
10.	Human Skill	95	2.50	105	3.61	3.06	3 rd	Agree

Aggregate mean = 2.86 and 2.90

The result as revealed in Table 2 indicated that respondents agreed to coordinating skill with mean scores of 3.30 and 3.60, time management skill with mean scores of 3.73 and 2.44, human Skill with mean scores of 2.50 and 3.61 and they disagreed to technical skill with mean scores of 2.35 and 2.49 and conceptual skill with mean scores of 2.40 and 2.34 as the organizing skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State. However, the aggregate mean shows that the female principals agree more organizing skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State than the male principals.

Test Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the time management skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State.

Table 3: z-test results for male and female principals on the time management skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State.

S/N	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	z-cal	z-tab	Remark
1	Male	95	2.66	1.88	198	1.79	1.96	Fail to reject Ho
2	Female	105	2.78	1.25				

Table 3 showed the result of the statistical significant test on the responses of male and female principals on the time management skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State. From the table, since the z-cal value of 1.79 is less than the z-crit. value of 1.96, there is no statistical significant difference between the opinion of male and female principals on the time management skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State.

Ho2; There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on the on the organizing skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State.

Table 4: z-test results for male and female principals on the on the organizing skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State.

S/N	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	z-cal	z-tab	Remark
1	Male	95	3.45	2.21	198	2.07	1.96	Reject Ho
2	Female	105	2.49	1.76				

Table 4 showed the result of the statistical significant test on the responses of male and female principals on the on the organizing skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State. From the table, since the z-cal value of 2.07 is higher than the z-crit. value of 1.96, there is a statistical significant difference between the opinion of male and female principals on the on the organizing skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State.

Summary of Findings

1. The findings of the study showed that respondents agreed to delegation skill, organizing skill, communication skill, planning skill, and they disagreed to prioritizing skill as the time management skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State. There is no statistical significant difference between the opinion of male and female principals on the time management skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State.

4. The findings of the study showed that respondents agreed to coordinating skill, time management skill, human Skill and they disagreed to technical skill and conceptual skill as the organizing skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State. There is a statistical significant difference between the opinion of male and female principals on the on the organizing skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State.

DISCUSSIONS

Time management skills adopted for secondary school administration

The findings of the study showed that respondents agreed to delegation skill, organizing skill, communication skill, planning skill, and they disagreed to prioritizing skill as the time management skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State. There is no statistical significant difference between the opinion of male and female principals on the time management skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State. This is in line with Obi (2003) who found out time management skills for effective communication involves identifying tasks to be performed, planned and scheduling organizational activities, prioritizing such activities, allocating time to the activities based on their level of importance so as to improve productivity. This corroborates with Ajayi (2007) who found that personal time analysis chart helps principals to study the use of their time and on the basis prepare a more useful personal time tables for their activities during the day and each week which allows principals to identify their time wasters.

Organizing skills adopted for secondary school administration

The findings of the study showed that respondents agreed to coordinating skill, time management skill, human Skill and they disagreed to technical skill and conceptual skill as the organizing skills adopted for secondary school

administration in Rivers State. There is a statistical significant difference between the opinion of male and female principals on the on the organizing skills adopted for secondary school administration in Rivers State. This in line with Okori (2011) who found out that organizing involves division of task or work, departmentalizing and delegation of authority and responsibility. This in line with Obi (2003) who also found that organizing entails identifying the task to be done, arranging them into jobs or roles for individuals and allocating them among employees into units or departments.

CONCLUSION

From the findings, the study concluded that when principals' managerial skills are being used effectively by the principal, there will also be effective administration of secondary schools in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were highlighted based on the findings of the study.

- School administrators should utilize the non-verbal and prioritizing skills meant for proper running of the school.
- Government should be more committed, by creating rooms for more leadership training for the schools and also monitor how the trainings are utilized.
- Individuals, organizations and communities should be encouraged to develop their schools before aspiring to be a principal or an administrator, both in school and outside school settings.
- School administrators or principals should seek knowledge from other institutions and related literatures on how to effectively utilize their skills.

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